

Nolan Windham

Sara Hammerman

Honors English 3 D

8 May 2019

A Buddhist Interpretation of Mid-twentieth Century American Literature

James Baldwin's *Sonny's Blues* and Arthur Miller's *Death of a Salesman* are texts which artfully and meaningfully illustrate the suffering underlying the American Dream. The illusions that motivate their characters demonstrate a Buddhist analysis of the world. By showing suffering while displaying the characters' illusions the reader can make the connection between these ideas.

The nature of attachment, suffering, reality, and meditation are described in The Four Noble Truths of Buddhism. The first truth is that suffering is a characteristic of existence. The second truth is the origin of suffering is attachment and the "active misconception of the nature of things: seeing pleasure where there is pain, beauty where there is ugliness, permanence where there is impermanence, and self where there is no self" (Lopez). The third truth is cessation of suffering, or nirvana. The fourth truth is the path through which nirvana is achieved which describes the practice of mindfulness and meditation. True suffering is mental but the mind can be controlled. "Problems and the absence of problems do not come from outside. Problems and the absence of problems, as well as all peace and all happiness, only come from your own mind. Your mind has the potential to stop the problems that come from your mind" (Zopa 3).

In the American Literature of the nineteen-fifties and sixties, the root cause of suffering, as is true for all suffering, is attachment, which release is both possible and demonstrated

through various forms of meditation. Suffering is anything that is considered to be unpleasant, causing pain or sadness. A common theme in James Baldwin's *Sonny's Blues* and Arthur Miller's *Death of a Salesman* is the experience of suffering. The suffering of all these people is the result of their attachment. Sonny is exposed to plenty of suffering. Sonny grew up in the desperate poverty of public housing projects. He wasn't happy with school. His relationship with his father was strained to the day he died. His mother then died, leaving his his brother as his last familial connection. He and his brother then had a falling out. He had nothing to turn to except the needle. Sonny's struggle with his heroin addiction is his form of suffering. The suffering of Willy Loman is absolutely clear. He does not live in the present moment. He is paranoid of all who surround him, jealous of his "successful" peers such as Charlie and family members such as his deceased brother Ben. He struggles with his belief that he might be a failure. His self-hatred is a prominent theme throughout the play and ultimately drives him to end his life. Willy's inability to fulfill his desires is a result of his unhealthy unconditional attachment to achieving them. Setting the stakes so unreasonably high without recourse made any form of failure fatal. Willy Loman fantasizes that he is a successful salesman and a good father. His fantasy does not reflect the truth. Willy builds and experiences an illusory world to in an instinctive attempt to cope with his reality of extreme suffering. Willy is so desperately attached to fulfilling society's expectations of him that he manufactures and experiences a reality that is illusory. This experience is not a mystery to Buddhist philosophers, in fact it happens to be the core tenet of Buddhist understanding. Treating the illusory as reality is another cause of suffering. "Truly every living being has the basic wish to experience happiness and avoid suffering. But so often, our attempts to find happiness end up only causing more pain" (Zopa 1). Willy is so desperately

infatuated with the illusion of the American Dream that his manic madness results from its unending unreachability.

Buddhist ideology asserts that attachment is the root cause of suffering. ““The root of suffering is attachment,” Buddha taught in the Pali canon” (“What Would Buddha, Jesus, and the Dalai Lama Think About the American Dream?”). Attachment is difficult to describe to the unfamiliar. There are linguistic and cultural barriers between Buddhist understanding and contemporary Western society. These obstacles likely contribute to lack of awareness of Buddhist theory. The concept of attachment can be best described through the Buddhist principle known as dependent arising which is the "general philosophy of all Buddhist systems" (H.H. Lama 37). It states “If this exists, that exists; if this ceases to exist, that also ceases to exist.” This simply describes that all phenomena exist in dependence of other phenomena. In more contemporary terms that the typical materialistic reader would better relate to, if one desires a luxury car and does not have a luxury car they experience a greater degree of displeasure than if they did possess a luxury car. If this person did not have desire for the luxury car they would not experience this displeasure. The confounding simplicity of this is, paradoxically, a deterrent from the acceptance of this principle among many of those who contemplate it.

Willy's attachment is clear and extensive. From the perspective of Willy Loman, success is defined purely based on the social and economic status of himself and his family. This is warranted by Willy's idolization of Ben, his wealthy brother, and his fantasization of being personally successful. Willy was driven to live in a reverie of his romanticized past, when "things were good." Willy looks back on his past when Biff was the star of the football team and bills were being paid. Willy desires to exist in a state of fulfillment so intensely that not only his

experience of his past memories becomes altered, but his experience of reality as well. Biff says “Pop, I’m nothing! I’m nothing, Pop. Can’t you understand that?” Willy hates considering that he and his family could be failures. It is his deepest fear, but it is his reality. Referring to Willy’s desire to lead a life of personal, economic, and familial success, Biff persists “Will you take that phony dream and burn it before something happens” (Miller 106). This clearly illustrates the function through which desire, attachment, and illusion lead to suffering. Biff’s usage of the words “phony dream” shows that Willy’s reveries are illusory and harmful manifestations of his desire for him and his boy to be successful. Biff’s suggestion that he forget that dream before “something happens” foreshadows what does happen: Willy’s suicide. Tibetan Buddhist scholar Lama Zopa Rinpoche explains “real happiness has nothing to do with the past, with our history, or our upbringing. Real happiness comes when we free ourselves from the dissatisfied mind of desire. Satisfaction comes when we give ourselves freedom from the always unhappy mind of desire” (Zopa 4).

It is through the Buddhist practice of mindfulness that one can see past what this illusory. Meditation is the temporary cessation of desire. While meditating, the only thing that exists in the mind’s eye is the breath. “Most of the time we are engaged in bringing to mind our desire for permanence, pleasure, and getting what we want.” “But by changing our habit and bringing to mind the interdependence of phenomena, we begin to see the conditioned, impermanent, and selfless nature of everything” (Mipham).

Biff, when working with his hands glimpses this freedom though it remains elusive. Ultimately, the Lomans are not freed, indeed Happy repeats the cycle: “All right boy. I’m gonna show you and everyone else that Willy Loman did not die in vain. He had a good dream. It’s the

only dream you can have- to come out number-one man. He fought it out here, and this is where I'm gonna win it for him" (Miller 138). This leads to a cycle of suffering, continuing with Happy's legacy of proving that his father did not die in vain by promising to become a successful salesman. This illustrates "Samsara, "the cycle of suffering," is a direct result of our desire for permanence."

Sonny's attachment is the use of heroin in a vacuum of personal support. "The urge for community and communion is a utopian urge, as is the desire to be "in control," as to be in control of one's own destiny is the very definition of freedom. But of course, trying to find those in a heroin-filled needle is the falsest of false utopian paths. Both community and control are illusions. As addiction takes hold, control turns to slavery; as life becomes centered around the desire for ever-increasing doses of the drug, the addict becomes utterly self-centered, making community impossible" (Farnell).

In *Sonny's Blues*, Sonny finally uses his blues to become free. It is his form of meditation. There is a meditative aspect to expression through jazz. There are similarities between musical expression and other practices of mindfulness such as meditation.

Buddhist philosophy is that meditation can set an individual free. Jazz is meditation. Baldwin points to the success of this action. "Sometimes, you know, and it was actually when I was most out of the world, I felt that I was in it, that I was with it, really, and I could play or I didn't really have to play, it just came out of me, it was there" (Baldwin 144). "Freedom lurked around us and I understood, at last, that he could help us to be free if we would listen, that he would never be free until we did." The narrator experiences and understands Sonny's suffering only when Sonny taps into his inner soul and plays.

At one point, Sonny comments on the connection he experiences with an impassioned singing member of street corner revival group. "While I was downstairs before, on my way here, listening to that woman sing, it struck me all of a sudden how much suffering she must have had to go through—to sing like that." Much like the soulful musical expression described, meditation is the practice of releasing attachment, and therefore releasing one's connection to suffering. Likewise, Sonny's music performed at the club presents his inner suffering for all who listen. Jazz is in present moment and outside normal cognition. Jazz removes the player from cognitive thinking and thus not thinking about attachments. Jazz flows just as the breath does. Many 20th century Jazz musicians such as John Coltrane, John McLaughlin, Don Cherry, Wayne Shorter, Yusef Lateef, Sonny Rollins, and Herbie Hancock have shared that they were inspired by meditation. John Coltrane said "My goal in meditating on this through music however remains... to uplift people as much as I can. To inspire them to realize more and more their capacities for living meaningful lives" (Murphy).

"The narrator is "aware that this was only a moment, that the world waited outside, as hungry as a tiger, and that trouble stretched above us, longer than the sky" (Baldwin 142). But it is real. It is similar to the Zen Buddhist concept of kenshou (見性), a moment of illumination, and Sonny, like a bodhisatva (菩薩), cannot be free until all are. Without realizing, he has followed through on his childhood dream of Indian enlightenment, metaphorically "walking barefoot through hot coals and arriving at wisdom" (Farnell). "The man who creates the music is hearing something else, is dealing with the roar rising from the void and imposing order on it as it hits the air. What is evoked in him, then, is of another order, more terrible because it has no words, and

triumphant, too, for that same reason. And his triumph, when he triumphs, is ours"
(Baldwin 111).

Each of the characters suffers and has illusions. The American dream is an illusion in both works. It is a living dream instead of a living reality. Reality is the suffering that Willy has on account of his disappointments and illusions. Reality is the suffering that Sonny has living in the projects. The absence of mindfulness is a recurring cycle of birth and rebirth as Willy is reborn into Happy. Meanwhile, a Buddhist can point to the mindfulness of jazz as a path for Sonny from Samsara to Nirvana.

“The happiness of material progress is artificial, just some kind of external excitement—the briefest flash of lightning in the dark. True joy, lasting joy, comes from the depths of the heart”

(Zopa 5).

Works Cited

Baldwin, James. "Sonny's Blues." *Going to Meet the Man*, The Dial Press, 1965, p. 139.

Farnell, David A. "Utopias false and true in Baldwin's" Sonny's blues"(アメリカ文化表象研究)." *福岡大学研究部論集. A, 人文科学編* 10.5 (2010): 7-14.

ci.nii.ac.jp/naid/110007818615/.

Lama, Dalai. *The Wheel of Life: Buddhist Perspectives on Cause and Effect*. Simon & Schuster, 2015.

Lopez, Donald S. "Four Noble Truths." *Encyclopædia Britannica*, Encyclopædia Britannica, inc., 14 Mar. 2017, www.britannica.com/topic/Four-Noble-Truths. Accessed 8 May 2019.

Miller, Arthur. *Death of a Salesman*. Dramatists Play Service, 1952.

Mipham, Sakyong. "The Myth of Permanence." *Lion's Roar*, Lion's Roar Foundation, 13 June 2017, www.lionsroar.com/the-myth-of-permanence/.

Murphy, Sean. "Trane of No-Thought: How Meditation Inspired Jazz Great John Coltrane." *Lion's Roar*, Lion's Roar Foundation, 31 Jan. 2018, www.lionsroar.com/trane-of-no-thought-how-meditation-inspired-jazz-great-john-coltrane/.

"What Would Buddha, Jesus, and the Dalai Lama Think About the American Dream?" *Dalai Lama Documentary Films – Transformational Films Featuring the Dalai Lama*, 22 Nov. 2015, www.dalailamafilm.com/what-would-buddha-jesus-and-the-dalai-lama-think-about-the-american-dream-1646.

Zopa Rinpoche, Lama. *How to Be Happy*. Simon & Schuster, 2008.